

ABOUT THE WORKSHOP

The community cross-fertilisation workshop, 'RDA for Health and Medical Data', brought chairs and members of RDA Working Groups (WGs) and Interest Groups (IGs) together, with members of the wider research data community, to share and discuss challenges, solutions and initiatives associated with managing health and medical data. Key findings of the workshop summarised herein will be used to direct the future strategy of the RDA community. Read more about the [community cross-fertilisation workshop series](#) in commemoration of the [RDA's 10th Anniversary](#).

CHALLENGES TO BE ADDRESSED WITHIN THE THEME OF HEALTH AND MEDICAL DATA

Data access

- Ensuring efficient, equitable, ethical and secure data access/sharing practices to mitigate global health crises, such as the COVID-19 pandemic.
- Understanding type and quantity of data, and time required to mitigate such crises.
- Harmonising patient consent procedures (e.g., machine actionable informed consent) across geographical and cultural boundaries.

Data quality, harmonisation and linkage

- Ensuring robustness, reliability, comparability and interoperability of health and medical data.
- Developing global data and metadata standards across different health and medical domains.
- Integrating research and clinical schemas with medical billing codes.
- Enabling data linkage (integration of data from different sources about the same subject) when data is anonymised for privacy protection.

Ethics

- Reducing risk of subject re-identification in de-identified data due to data linkage.
- Understanding how to share high-dimensional genomic data without re-identification of subject or relatives (e.g., genealogical databases).
- Understanding approaches (methods, sample sizes, population characteristics) to reduce (re-)identification risk.
- Achieving anonymisation of data without loss of data value and quality.
- Security and privacy risks of employing Artificial Intelligence (AI) in health and medical domains.
- Exploitation of health and medical data for creating private goods/for profit actions.
- [Dual Use Research of Concern \(DURC\)](#), e.g., health and medical research that is intended to provide a clear benefit but which could easily be misapplied to cause harm.

Social and cultural barriers

- Lack of knowledge and confidence to securely manage and share data between different stakeholders (e.g., using data generated by pharmaceutical companies).
- Lack of trust in health and medical data sharing workflows and systems (e.g., using trusted research environments [TREs]).
- Balancing security of TREs with ease of use to encourage researchers to adopt secure data management and sharing practice.

PARTICIPATING GROUP & WORKSHOP LEAD*

[RDA COVID-19 Working Group](#) Workshop leads:

[Anne Cambon-Thomsen](#) & [Priyanka Pillai](#)

Outputs:

- [RDA COVID-19 Guidelines and Recommendations \(draft versions\)](#)
- [Sharing COVID-19 Epidemiology Data](#)
- [The final version of the RDA COVID-19 Recommendations and Guidelines for Data Sharing, published 30 June 2020](#)
- [DS-Wizard Navigation Tool for the RDA COVID-19 Recommendations](#)
- [MindMap Navigation Tool for the RDA COVID-19 Recommendations](#)
- [Enhancing Access to Research Data to Combat COVID-19: Recommendations to Funders](#)
- [RDA COVID-19 Zotero Library - March 2021](#)

See [community group card](#)

[Health Data Interest Group](#)
Workshop lead: [Edwin Morley-Fletcher](#)

See [community group card](#)

[Privacy Implications of Research Data Sets Interest Group](#)
Workshop lead: [Joerg Geiger](#)

See [community group card](#)

[Sensitive Data Interest Group](#)
Workshop lead: [Nichola Burton](#)
Output: RDA17 Plenary session: [Establishing a Sensitive Data Interest Group](#)

See [community group card](#)

*The workshop lead collected challenges, solutions and initiatives in preparation for the workshop which were presented during the workshop on behalf of their group.

SOLUTIONS TO ADDRESS THE CHALLENGES

Raising awareness, training and education

- Produce clear definitions to enable identification and categorisation of 'sensitive', 'health' and 'personal' data.
- Draft guidelines for improving health and medical data quality, and establish verifiable data quality criteria.
- Determine minimum data/data fields required for health and medical research and policy to improve collaboration, data comparability, linkage and harmonisation.
- Raise awareness, and provide education and training for researchers about creating data management plans, obtaining ethical approval for projects and [General Data Protection Regulation \(GDPR\)](#) in global context (medical and non-medical).
- Organise workshops and ongoing engagement with various stakeholder communities to develop common health and medical data/metadata standards and vocabularies to enhance data quality and interoperability.

Privacy preservation

- Conduct a survey and evaluation of privacy preserving techniques and data anonymisation tools and services.
- Devise guidelines, privacy models and boundary conditions for data anonymisation that include legal considerations for the management and sharing of sensitive data.
- Adapt Humanities and Social Science (HASS) techniques for appropriate management of qualitative health and medical data.
- Employ trusted third-party entities for the appropriate storage and management of pseudonymised data and data linkage.

Technical infrastructure

- Facilitate dialogue between stakeholders (e.g., researchers, data providers and infrastructure providers) to better understand challenges of using TREs for managing sensitive data.
- Link TREs together to enable federated query and safe, secure and efficient data sharing.
- Develop tools, systems and services for distributed curation of datasets that enable different levels of authorisation to data and metadata.

ACTIONS FOR THE RDA COMMUNITY

Share first-hand experience of RDA COVID-19 Working Groups. Create a 'toolkit' reflecting on the successes, lessons learned and steps taken to produce guidelines and best practices for timely data sharing during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Create a directory of health and medical data initiatives. Map and inventorise various tools, resources, systems, services, organisations and communities related to health and medical research data domains.

INITIATIVES & RESOURCES OF INTEREST

- [RDA Raising FAIRness in health data and health research performing organisations \(HRPOs\) Working Group](#)
- [RDA Blockchain Applications in Health Working Group](#)
- [RDA Ethics and Social Aspects of Data Interest Group](#)
- [RDA Artificial Intelligence and Data Visitation \(AIDV\) Working Group](#)
- [Trusted Research Environments for Sensitive Data: FAIRness for "Closed" Data and Processes](#) Birds of a Feather session at RDA 20th Plenary, Gothenburg
- [European Health Data Space \(EHDS\)](#)
- [German Medical Informatics Initiative \(German MII\)](#)
- [National Research Data Infrastructure for Personal Health Data \(NFDI4Health\)](#)
- [Network University Medicine \(NUM\)](#)
- [Swiss Personalized Health Network \(SPHN\)](#)
- [FAIRification of health-related data using semantic web technologies in the Swiss Personalized Health Network](#) (journal article)
- [UK Health Data Research Alliance](#)
- [Health Studies Australian National Data Asset \(HeSANDA\)](#)
- [Data and Analytics Research Environments UK \(DARE UK\)](#)
- [Request for comments: Initial draft of the DARE UK federated architecture blueprint for sensitive data research](#)
- [SARA: Semi-Automated Risk Assessment of Data Provenance and Clinical Free-Text in TREs](#) (DARE UK)
- [SATRE: Standardised Architecture for Trusted Research Environments](#) (DARE UK)
- [Observational Health Data Sciences and Informatics \(OHDSI\)](#)
- [Global Alliance for Genomics and Health \(GA4GH\)](#)
- [BioMedIT](#)
- [Goldacre Review Better, Broader, Safer: Using Health Data for Research and Analysis](#)
- [International transfers of personal data for health research following Schrems II: a problem in need of a solution](#) (journal article)
- [German MII: Template text for patient consent](#)
- [Swiss academies for arts and sciences: General consent](#)
- [Ecosystem Digital Twins in Healthcare \(EDITH\)](#)
- [ClinicalStudyDataRequest.com](#)
- [Logical Observation Identifiers Names and Codes \(LOINC\)](#)
- [SNOMED CT: structured clinical vocabulary for use in an electronic health record](#)
- [International Statistical Classification of Diseases and Related Health Problems 10th Revision \(ICD-10\)](#)
- [LH7 FHIR](#) (Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources)
- [Health Data Governance Principles](#)
- [FAIR, CARE and TRUST principles](#)
- [The FAIRplus Fellowship Programme](#) (Transformative Digital Skills for Healthcare)
- [The FAIR Cookbook](#)

WORKSHOP PARTICIPANTS

1. **Aytan Ahmadova**, Institute of Information Technology, Baku, Azerbaijan, [0000-0003-1355-7425](https://doi.org/0000-0003-1355-7425)
2. **Christine Allan**, Clinical Research Facility, University College Cork, Ireland
3. **Owen Appleton**, SIB Personalised Health Informatics Group / BioMedIT, Switzerland, [0000-0002-2571-6860](https://doi.org/0000-0002-2571-6860)
4. **Rob Baxter**, DARE UK, UK, [0000-0002-3693-8725](https://doi.org/0000-0002-3693-8725)
5. **John Brown**, Australian Research Data Commons, Australia, [0000-0002-6118-577X](https://doi.org/0000-0002-6118-577X)
6. **Nichola Burton**, Australian Research Data Commons, Australia, [0000-0003-4470-4846](https://doi.org/0000-0003-4470-4846)
7. **Lauren Cadwallader**, PLOS, UK, [0000-0002-7571-3502](https://doi.org/0000-0002-7571-3502)
8. **Giulia Caldoni**, Alma Mater Università di Bologna, Italy, [0000-0001-6105-721X](https://doi.org/0000-0001-6105-721X)
9. **Anne Cambon-Thomsen**, CNRS, Toulouse, France, [0000-0001-8793-3644](https://doi.org/0000-0001-8793-3644)
10. **Matt Cannon**, Taylor & Francis, UK, [0000-0002-1496-8392](https://doi.org/0000-0002-1496-8392)
11. **Romain David**, European Research Infrastructure on Highly Pathogenic Agents (ERINHA), Belgium, [0000-0003-4073-7456](https://doi.org/0000-0003-4073-7456)
12. **Chris Erdmann**, Michael J. Fox Foundation, USA [0000-0003-2554-180X](https://doi.org/0000-0003-2554-180X)
13. **Lala Garayeva**, Institute of Information Technology, Baku, Azerbaijan, [0000-0003-2109-4280](https://doi.org/0000-0003-2109-4280)
14. **Julia Gehrman**, Biomedical Informatics, University Hospital Cologne, Germany, [0000-0002-4101-5458](https://doi.org/0000-0002-4101-5458)
15. **Joerg Geiger**, University of Wuerzburg - ibdw Biobank, Germany, [0000-0002-7689-531X](https://doi.org/0000-0002-7689-531X)
16. **Nancy Gomez Aguirre**, Universidad Carlos III de Madrid, Spain, [0000-0002-6218-6248](https://doi.org/0000-0002-6218-6248)
17. **Anupama Gururaj**, NIH, USA
18. **Zarifa Jabrayilova**, Institute of Information Technology, Baku, Azerbaijan, [0000-0002-9661-5805](https://doi.org/0000-0002-9661-5805)
19. **Lene Krøl Andersen**, Computerome, DTU, Denmark
20. **Masuma Mammadova**, Institute of Information Technology, Baku, Azerbaijan, [0000-0002-2205-1023](https://doi.org/0000-0002-2205-1023)
21. **Priyanka Pillai**, University of Melbourne, Australia, [0000-0002-7142-4519](https://doi.org/0000-0002-7142-4519)
22. **Andrea Popescu**, Regina Elena National Cancer Institute, Italy, [0009-0002-7856-6277](https://doi.org/0009-0002-7856-6277)
23. **Mario Reale**, GÉANT, Amsterdam, The Netherlands, [0000-0002-3502-258X](https://doi.org/0000-0002-3502-258X)
24. **Claire Rye**, New Zealand eScience Infrastructure/University of Auckland, New Zealand, [0000-0003-4630-7836](https://doi.org/0000-0003-4630-7836)
25. **Mandar Sahasrabuddhe**, Kovid BioAnalytics Pvt Ltd, India, [0000-0002-9932-9572](https://doi.org/0000-0002-9932-9572)
26. **Nargiz Shikhaliyeva**, Institute of Information Technology, Baku, Azerbaijan, [0000-0002-5427-0765](https://doi.org/0000-0002-5427-0765)
27. **Jan Wiebelitz**, Leibniz Universität Hannover, Germany, [0000-0002-9158-7024](https://doi.org/0000-0002-9158-7024)

For more information about the RDA community cross-fertilisation workshop series, please contact Community Development Managers, Connie Clare (connie.clare@rda-foundation.org) and Kathryn Barker (kathryn.barker@ardc.edu.au).

To become a member of the RDA, register [here](#)